

EFFECT OF FLIPPED CLASSROOM STRATEGY TO PHYSICS ACHIEVEMENT AMONG SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS' IN KAUMA SUB-COUNTY, KILIFI COUNTY KENYA

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15369711>

Published Date: 09-May-2025

Abstract: Globally, the flipped classroom strategy has emerged as an innovative and transformative approach to teaching and learning, aimed at promoting active student engagement and improving academic outcomes, particularly in Physics education. Despite its increasing adoption worldwide, the effectiveness of this approach in resource-constrained settings like rural Kenya remains underexplored. This study examined the effect of the flipped classroom strategy on students' achievement in Physics among secondary school learners in Kauma Sub-County, Kilifi County, Kenya. The rationale for the study stems from the persistent low performance in Physics in the region, calling for alternative pedagogical approaches that can enhance conceptual understanding and learner motivation. A quasi-experimental research design was employed, comparing an experimental group exposed to the flipped classroom strategy with a control group taught through conventional methods. Data were collected using pre-tests and post-tests to assess achievement levels. These results suggest that the flipped classroom strategy enhances conceptual understanding and active learning, offering a promising approach to improving Physics education in Kenyan secondary schools. The study recommends the integration of flipped learning approaches into teacher training and classroom instruction to advance quality education in science subjects.

Keywords: Flipped Classroom Strategy, Physics Education, Student Achievement, Innovative Pedagogy, Rural Secondary Schools in Kenya.

1. INTRODUCTION

Flipped classroom strategy is gaining popularity in recent years as an innovative strategy to teaching and learning. In this strategy, students are given an opportunity to interact with the learning materials prior to the class time trying to understand concepts on their own while class time is used for hands-on and interactive learning activities (Musdi, Agustyani & Tasman 2019). This strategy was initially used as a peer instruction strategy in 1990s where Harvard University students read printed materials before class time waiting for discussions and problem solving activities during class time (Baker 2016). Research has shown that this strategy can enhance student performance by promoting active learning, critical thinking, and engagement. For example, a study by Chen, Lui & Martinelli (2018) found that students in flipped classrooms performed significantly better in assessments as compared to those in traditional settings. They attributed the success to increase of

opportunities for collaborative learning and problem-solving during class time. Additionally, meta-analysis of 17 researches on flipped classroom strategy done in China by Lo, Hew & Chen (2017) showed that the flipped classroom strategy led to moderate improvements in student achievement, particularly in STEM subjects.

The early exposure of learning materials to students in this strategy is accomplished through the use relevant films, animations, handouts, and hands-on materials that align with the subject matter to be covered (Akçayır & Akçayır, 2018). This strategy is guided by learning theories that emphasizes on experiential, self-directed and active learning.

With the high development rate of technology and innovations in the world, flipped classroom is being adopted globally and across all educational levels (Hew, Bai & Huang, 2021). For example, many primary and K-12 schools in North America are using flipped classroom strategy to enhance personalized and active engagement by allowing students to access pre-class learning materials on Khan Academy and TED-ed online platforms. Also tertiary schools facilitates STEM subject using this strategy as learners access pre-class materials on Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs) platform (Deng 2019).

In Europe, U.K and Scandinavian countries have been using flipped classroom strategy to enhance autonomy and differentiated learning (Mitsiou, 2019). Government initiatives towards modern education in China are emphasizing educational institutions to adopt blended learning approaches with the support of DingTalk and Tencent classroom. International schools in the United Arab Emirates uses flipped learning to promote critical thinking and problem-solving skills. Furthermore, Saudi universities adopt flipped classrooms as part of broader efforts to modernize and improve the quality of higher education. However, the effectiveness of the flipped classroom strategy varies based on implementation and context. For instance, Zainuddin and Perera (2019) highlighted that while flipped classrooms generally lead to positive outcomes, the success largely depends on the quality of pre-class materials and the effectiveness of in-class activities. In higher education, the flipped classroom strategy has been particularly beneficial for improving student performance and engagement in complex subjects.

In spite of this, there is low growth rate of technology development and inadequate infrastructure in Africa; efforts are ongoing to introduce flipped learning in schools (Baingana, 2024). For instance, in Nigeria, only a few private schools are using flipped classroom strategy. A study by Egara, & Mosimege (2024) on flipped classroom and mathematics achievements to senior secondary in Nigeria showed a positive impact to the students' performance in the subject. Also only Universities in South Africa have explored flipped learning to improve student engagement and address large class sizes, Parker et al (2022). In Kenya, Universities like University of Nairobi and Kenyatta University are using flipped classrooms majorly for training medicine and engineering courses. However, there are a few studies done in public secondary schools in Kenya indicating positive results but it has not been embraced in many schools in the country. For example, Chebotib, Too, & Ongeti, (2022) studied the effects of the flipped learning strategy on students' biology achievement in Uasin Gishu County extra county schools and recommended that it is a potential tool to better performance of students though the schools were homogeneous hence the results could not be generalized. In the coastal region of Kenya only one study on flipped classroom and physics performance was done in Mombasa county private secondary schools and the findings were positive towards the strategy. In Kilifi County, no school has embraced the use of flipped classroom for their instruction.

Studies on flipped classroom strategy show that, students in flipped classroom get more engaged during instructions. This increased participation is attributed to the fact that students have already been exposed to the material before class, allowing them to come prepared with questions and ideas as stated by Cardaciotto (2018). Furthermore, (Wagner, Gegenfurtner & Urhahne, 2020) stated that flipped learning strategy generally shows better student outcomes as compared to traditional lecture-based methods. However, most of the available studies have focused on Western educational contexts. The focus on the western education led to a noticeable lack of adequate presence of studies on flipped strategy in the African context, especially at the secondary level. There was a need to address this gap. This study was therefore conducted in Kauma Sub County, a rural area in Kenya which is one of the countries in Africa.

The general performance of physics for the past five years in Kenya has been low. According to the KNEC 2022 results report, the subject recorded mean scores that are below average for seven consecutive years. Table 1.1 shows the mean score of physics scored in Kenya from 2018 to 2022 as per the 2022 KCSE Physics Report.

Table 1.1: Physics mean score as per the 2022 KCSE report

Year	Physics Mean marks score (%)
2018	21.61
2019	21.73
2020	23.69
2021	19.90
2022	22.04

The dismal performance in the general performance is highly contributed by the extremely low performance from the schools in rural areas. Kauma Sub-County being one of the rural areas, most schools in the have been performing lowly as evidenced by the schools’ KCSE mean points records in the subjects in the previous years. The data in the Table 1.2 shows the mean score of physics for 9 schools in Kauma Sub-County for the past 6 years as per the sub-county records

Table 1.2: History of Physics performances of the ten schools in Kauma Sub- County

School	Physics mean score (grading points)					
	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
Jaribuni boys	3.26	3.48	3.12	2.98	3.42	3.66
Mayowe Secondary	1.98	2.42	1.67	1.87	2.45	2.21
Palakumi secondary school	2.48	2.34	1.93	2.23	2.76	2.46
Tsanzeni secondary school	-	1.97	1.51	1.67	2.31	2.39
Majajani secondary school	1.76	1.85	1.52	1.97	2.23	2.13
Konjora secondary school	-	-	-	-	1.67	2.03
Vyambani secondary school	2.51	2.76	2.34	2.47	3.12	2.94
Sosoni secondary school	2.14	1.96	1.45	1.68	1.94	2.09
Mwapula secondary schools	-	-	-	-	1.48	1.74

Numerous factors, including ineffective teaching strategies, poor study habits, inadequate preparation, and challenges with mathematical and analytical skills, are blamed for the poor performance (Michael, & Wumi, 2020). The ineffective methods of instruction in classrooms served as the base for this study as it aimed at testing whether flipped classroom strategy can help in improving the students’ performance in the subject by using it to teach electrostatics (I), a topic in form 1.

The implementation of the flipped classroom strategy in Kenya has shown promising results, particularly in science subjects. A study conducted by Mutambuki and Fynewever (2017) in Nairobi secondary schools found that students in a flipped physics classroom performed significantly better in both formative and summative assessments compared to their peers in traditional classrooms. The study also reported improved student attitudes towards physics and increased engagement during lessons. Though the findings were positive in this area, this was an urban center of study. Kauma Sub County is a remote area in Kenya. There is a need to do a similar research in a rural area to assess the effectiveness of the flipped strategy. This justified the study.

SPECIFIC OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

To determine the effect of the flipped classroom strategy on academic achievement of physics in secondary schools in Kauma sub-county, Kilifi County, Kenya

RESEARCH HYPOTHESES

H0: Flipped classroom strategy does not significantly improve students' academic achievement in physics

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Literature Review

The flipped classroom strategy, an instructional model that delivers theoretical content outside class—often via videos—and emphasizes interactive activities during face-to-face sessions, has been widely recognized as a student-centered approach that enhances engagement and understanding in STEM education. Globally, this approach has gained traction due

to its alignment with constructivist theories of learning, which emphasizes active participation in knowledge construction. Studies have shown that the flipped classroom model promotes deeper conceptual understanding and facilitates differentiated learning (Wang et al., 2021). In Physics education, where abstract concepts often pose a challenge to learners, the flipped classroom has been found to improve comprehension through visualization and practical engagement (Ahmed & Idris, 2022).

Research across various countries supports the positive impact of the flipped classroom on students' academic performance. A meta-analysis conducted by Zhang et al. (2023) revealed that flipped classroom interventions significantly improved academic outcomes, particularly in science subjects, compared to traditional lecture-based instruction. Similarly, in Nigeria, Oboh and Eze (2022) found that secondary school students exposed to flipped learning in Physics outperformed their peers in conventional classrooms, with notable gains in problem-solving skills and content retention. These findings point to the importance of interactive and student-centered methodologies in addressing challenges associated with low performance in technical subjects like Physics.

In the African context, and specifically in Kenya, the adoption of flipped classrooms remains limited due to infrastructural, pedagogical, and technological challenges. However, some recent pilot studies have shown promise. For instance, Mutiso and Mwangi (2021) found that Kenyan students who accessed video lectures and simulations before class demonstrated improved participation and higher test scores in Physics. Their study emphasized that the flipped approach is especially effective in rural settings when combined with mobile-based learning and community ICT centers. Nonetheless, barriers such as limited internet access and teachers' digital literacy remain significant hurdles to large-scale implementation (Njuguna & Karani, 2024).

Despite the growing body of evidence supporting flipped classrooms, there remains a gap in localized studies focusing on under-resourced and rural contexts like Kauma Sub-County. This gap justifies the need for research to evaluate the effectiveness of this strategy within the socio-economic and infrastructural realities of rural Kenyan schools. Furthermore, studies are needed to assess not just academic performance but also student motivation, teacher preparedness, and the sustainability of technology-enhanced instruction. Addressing these dimensions will provide a comprehensive understanding of how the flipped classroom model can be adapted to improve Physics achievement and contribute to educational equity in Kenya and similar settings (Kamau & Otieno, 2025).

3. METHODOLOGY AND RESEARCH DESIGN

This study adopted quantitative research methodology and adopted Solomon IV non-equivalent Quasi-experiment design. This design comprises of four randomly selected groups that participate in data collection. Two of the groups are treated as experimental groups and the other two becomes the control groups (Wanjala, 2020). The purpose this design is to test whether the treatment has an impact to the outcome. In this study, four schools were to be randomly selected from the ten of schools located in Kauma Sub-County, Kilifi County Kenya. From the four groups, two schools were to be experimental and the other two schools were to be the control groups. One experimental and one control school were to be subjected to a pretest achievement score test before the treatment. Thereafter, all selected schools were to be taught the same topic, Electrostatics (I), for a period of two weeks. The experimental schools were taught using the flipped classroom strategy while the control schools were taught using the conventional traditional methods. Thereafter, all groups were to be subjected to a post-test achievement test as summarized in table 3.1. The effects of maturation and history will be controlled by having two groups taking pre- test and post-tests. To avoid contamination, the treatment and control groups were to be from different schools. The regression effects were taken care of by two groups not taking the pre-tests.

The pre-test was to be treated as a normal classroom test that students regularly take in the course of instruction while the post test was to be taken as a normal test that is administered after a topic has been covered. The Physics teachers in the two experimental schools were to be given a teaching module that was to guide them on how to teach the topics when students were on recess. For a school with many form one streams, all the streams were to be treated the same, however, only the results from one stream in each school was analyzed for testing the hypotheses of the study.

Data presentation

In this study, data was presented using tables.

Table 1.3: Research design

GROUP	PRETEST	TREATMENT	POST-TEST
E ₁	√	√	√
E ₂	-	√	√
C ₁	√	-	√
C ₂	-	-	√

Random sampling was used to identify the participants of this study. Out of the four schools sampled, two of them were experimental while the other two were control groups. Therefore, four papers were cut, the papers were written E1, E2, C1 and C2. The physics teachers from the four sampled schools were to select a piece of paper randomly. Those who randomly selected E1 and E2 became the Experimental groups while those who picked the papers written C1 and C2 became the control groups of the study. The form one physics teachers from the E1 and E2 were taken through the teaching module which they used to teach the electrostatic (I) topic. The C1 and C2 groups taught the same topic with the traditional convectional instruction method.

Three out of the four schools that were involved had more than one stream. All the streams were treated the same but data from one stream was to be analyzed. To identify the stream whose data was to be analyzed, random numbers equivalent to the number of streams of the form one classes were written with one of them written 'yes' while the rest were written 'no', then one student from each stream picked one of the papers randomly. The data of stream from which the one that picked 'yes' belonged to, was analyzed for this study. Following this procedure, three physics teachers and 182 students from the four sampled schools were involved in the study. The 182 students were distributed as shown in table 4.1.

Table 1.4: Distribution of the sampled population

E1	32
E2	56
C1	43
C2	51

4. FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

A flipped classroom teaching module was prepared for Electrostatics (I). Before the module was put into practice, one experimental group E1 and one control group C1 were subjected to a pretest achievement score test. The E1 group had 32 students while the C1 group had 43 students, therefore, a total of 75 form 1 physics students sat for the pretest achievement score test. The pretest test was summing up to 30 marks. After the students had done the pretest, the papers were marked and recorded. Table 4.1 shows the summary of the scores attained by the experimental group 1 pretest.

Table 1.5: A summary of the pretest achievement scores of the experimental group 1

E1 pretest scores

marks	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1-5	21	65.6	65.6	65.6
6-10	6	18.8	18.8	84.4
11-16	5	15.6	15.6	100.0
Total	32	100.0	100.0	

Table 1.5 shows that, out of the 32 students who sat for the pretest in the experimental group 1, 21 (65.6%) of them scored marks ranging between 1 to 5 marks. Further, the table shows that, 6 (18.8 %) students scored from 6 to 10. 5 (15.6 %) students scored above 10 marks before they were subjected to the flipped module. From this the researcher concluded that

none of the students in the E1 class could score more than half of the total score in Electrostatic (I). This concurs with a study by Kaleli (2021) on a study about the effect of individualized online instruction on TPACK skills and achievement in piano lessons.

Further, the study sought to check the pretest achievement scores of the control group as shown on Table 1.6

Table 1.6: A summary of the pretest achievement scores of the control group 1

C1 pretest scores

Marks	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1-5	33	76.7	76.7	76.7
6-10	7	16.3	16.3	93.0
11-15	3	7.0	7.0	100.0
Total	43	100.0	100.0	

Table 1.6 shows the score summary of 43 students in the control group 1 who sat for the pretest achievement test on Electrostatic (I). The table shows that, 33 (76.7%) students scored from 1 to 5 marks, this range had the highest percentage of the total percentage of the students who sat for the pretest in the control group. Furthermore, 7 (16.3%) students scored from 6 to 10 marks out of the total 30 marks that they were to score. Those who scored from 11 to 15 marks were 3, which is 7% of the control group population who did the pretest. From the findings the study concluded that in the C1 group none scored above 15 marks.

The descriptive statistics of the two pretest scores were calculated with the help of SPSS 16 and summarized as shown in table 1.6 and table 1.7 for the E1 and C1 respectively.

Table 1.7: A summary of the descriptive statistics of E1 pretest scores

E1 pretest Scores Descriptive Statistics

	N	Range	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Variance
Marks	32	13	1	14	13.844	3.244	10.523
Valid N (listwise)	32						

Table 1.7 indicates that, 32 students did the pretest in the E1 group. The highest score was 14 marks while the lowest score was 1 mark. Therefore, the range of the maximum and minimum score was 13 marks. The mean mark was 3.8 438 with a standard deviation of 3.24395

Table 1.8: A summary of the descriptive statistics of C1 pretest scores

C1 Pretest Descriptive Statistics

	N	Range	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Variance
C1 pretest	43	11.00	1.00	12.00	3.3721	2.96827	8.811
Valid N (listwise)	43						

Table 1.8 shows that 43 students sat for the pretest achievement score test on Electrostatic (I). The highest mark score in the C1 class pretest was 12 marks, while the lowest mark was 1 mark giving a range of 11 marks. The C1 class had a mean of 3.3721 marks in the pretest score test with a standard deviation of 2.96827.

Comparing these two pretest descriptive statistics for the score of the two groups, we note that, the minimum score for the two groups was the same, which is 1 mark out of 30 marks. The maximum mark differed with only two marks between the E1 and the C1 group with 14 marks and 12 marks respectively. This indicate that none of the two groups had students who scored half the total marks and above which concurs with a study by Nantha et al (2024) on enhancing ICT literacy and achievement using a blended learning model for Thai business administration students. Further, an independent t-test was conducted with the help of SPSS 16 with $\alpha = 0.05$ between the achievement scores of E1 pretest and the C1 Electrostatic (I) pretest scores to test whether the groups were of the same capacity before the treatment and the findings were as shown in table 1.9

Table 1.9: Independent Samples Test between E1 and C1 pretest results

		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means				
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference
SCORE	EVA	.410	.524	-.251	73	.802	-.17951	.71422
	EVNA			-.247	62.737	.805	-.17951	.72561

EVA -Equal variances assumed

EVNA -Equal variances not assumed

From table 1.9, the Levene’s test for equality of variance indicates a significance of 0.524 which is greater than the alpha value of 0.05 that was used. This showed that the variances were equal. The table also indicates that the t values of the equal variance assumed and that of the equal variance not assumed were -0.251 and -0.247 respectively. The degrees of freedom were 73 and 62.737. The significances of the 2-tailed t tests were 0.802 and 0.805 for equal variance assumed and equal variance not assumed respectively. 0.802 and $0.805 > 0.05$, therefore, there was no statistical difference between the pretest achievement scores on Electrostatic (I) for E1 and C1. To confirm this finding one way ANOVA was conducted on the pretest achievement test score and the results were as summarized in table 1.10

Table 1.10: ANOVA results between E1 and C1 pretest results

ANOVA					
PRETEST	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	56.885	4	14.221	1.426	.252
Within Groups	269.333	27	9.975		
Total	326.219	31			

Table 1.10 indicates that the sum of squares between groups was 58.885 while that of within groups was 269.333. The degrees of freedom between groups were 4 while within groups the degrees of freedom were 27. The mean square between and within the groups were 14.221 and 9.975 respectively. Also table 4.6 indicates that the F- value was 1.426. The critical value of the one way ANOVA calculated was 0.252. Since $0.252 > 0.05$, therefore, there was no statistical difference between the pretest achievement scores of E1 and those of C1. Following this, a conclusion was made that the two groups were initially of the same level before the treatment. From The findings of the study, the research concluded that the two groups were initially of the same level before the treatment. The study concurs with a study by Bulus (2021) on non-equivalent pretest – posttest design. From these findings the researcher concluded that the two groups were initially of the same level before the treatment. The study concurs with a study by Bulus (2021) on non-equivalent pretest – posttest design.

After the pretest, all the four groups were taught the same topic, electrostatics (I). The two experimental groups were taught using the flipped classroom strategy while the control groups were taught using the traditional convectional strategies for a period of two weeks.

After the treatment, all the four groups were subjected to a posttest achievement score test. The test was up to 30 marks. Thereafter, the tests were marked and recorded.

The posttest scores of the two groups E and C groups were summarized as shown in table 1.11 and 1.12 respectively.

Table 1.11: A summary of the E posttest achievement scores

Experimental groups posttest achievement scores.

	Frequency	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 1-5	6	6.8	6.8
6-10	14	15.9	22.7
11-15	15	17.0	39.8
16-20	26	29.5	69.3
21-25	23	26.1	95.5
26-30	4	4.5	100.0
Total	88	100.0	

Table 1.11 indicates that those who scored 1 to 5 marks were 6 students covering 6.8% of the total class size, those who scored 6 to 10 marks were 14 students which was 15.9%, those who scored 11 to 15 marks were 15 (17.0 %), those who scored 16 to 20 marks were 26 (29.5%) students, and those who scored 21 to 25 were 23 (26.1%) students while those who scored 26 to 30 were 4 (4.5%) students. The descriptive statistics of this data was summarized as shown in table 4.8

Table 1.12: Experimental groups Posttest Scores Descriptive Statistics

	N	Range	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Variance
Marks	88	25	3	28	17.344	6.553	42.943
Valid N (listwise)	88						

This table indicates that, the range of experimental group posttest scores was 25 marks. The highest score was 28 marks and the minimum score was 3 marks. The mean mark of the scores was 17.344 with a standard deviation of 6.553 and the variance of 42.943. Based on these findings the researcher concluded that students achieved better after they are taken through the concepts of Electrostatic (I). This concurs with the findings of (Hasanova, Abduazizov, & Khujakulov, 2021).

Moreover, the study did descriptive statistics for the control group (*the C posttest*) as shown on table 1.13.

Table 1.13: Control group Posttest Score

	Frequency	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 1-5	13	13.8	13.8
6-10	29	30.9	44.7
11-15	38	40.4	85.1
16-20	11	11.7	96.8
21-25	3	3.2	100.0
Total	94	100.0	

From table 1.13 out of 94 student, students who scored from 1 to 5 marks in the posttest achievement test on Electrostatic (I) were 13 (13.8%), those who scored 6 to 10 marks were 29 (30.9%), those who scored 11 to 15 marks were 38 (40.4%), those who scored 16 to 20 marks were 11 (11.7%) and those who scored 21 to 25 marks were 3 (3.2%) students

Further, an item on the questionnaire sought to establish C1 posttest descriptive statistics as shown on Table 1.14

Table 1.14: C post-test descriptive statistics

Descriptive Statistics for C post-test

	N	Range	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Variance
Marks	94	23	2	25	12.97	5.521	30.477
Valid N (listwise)	94						

From Table 1.14 out of 94 posttest scores, the range was 23 marks as a result of the maximum score being 25 and the minimum score being 2 marks. The mean score of posttest scores was 12.97 with a standard deviation and variance of 5.521 and 30.477 respectively.

Further, the study sought to identify the effect of the flipped classroom strategy to student’s achievement in secondary school physics in students in Kauma Sub-County, the post-test achievement scores and the pretest scores of all the experimental and control groups were analyzed and compared using one way ANOVA inferential test to determine their statistical difference with a confidence level of 0.05 with the help of SPSS 16 as shown on table 1.15.

Table 1.15: One-way ANOVA between E1 and E2 posttest achievement scores

ANOVA

E1E2	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	1335.814	20	66.791	1.819	.036
Within Groups	2459.958	67	36.716		
Total	3795.773	87			

Table 1.15 indicates that, the sum of squares between and within the groups were 1335.814 and 2459.958 respectively. It also shows that the degrees of freedom between and within the groups were 20 and 67 respectively. 66.791 and 36.716 were the mean squares between and with the groups respectively. F-value for the ANOVA test for E1E2 and C1C2 posttest scores was 1.819. The critical value obtained from the analysis of variance was 0.036. Since $0.036 < 0.05$ hence the null hypothesis stated earlier was rejected. To confirm this finding, paired t-test was run between the same data and the finding summarized as in table 1.16

Table 1.16: Paired Samples Test for E1E2 and C1C2 posttest achievement scores

	Paired Differences					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
				Lower	Upper			
Pair 1 C1C2 - E1E2	-4.90900	8.47800	.90370	-6.70540	-3.11277	-5.432	87	.000

Table 1.16 indicate that the standard deviation and the standard mean error were 8.48(2dp) and 0.90 (2dp) respectively. The t-value was -5.432 with 87 degrees of freedom. Further, it indicates a significance of 0.000 which is less than the α -value of 0.05 leading to a second rejection of the H_0 . The study therefore concluded that that flipped classroom strategy significantly improved students' academic achievement in Electrostatic (I). The study therefore concluded that that flipped

classroom strategy significantly improved students' academic achievement in Electrostatic (I). This concurred with the findings of a study by Wei, Chen, Yang, Liu, Zong, Zhai and Kinshuk (2020) who conducted an experiment to evaluate the effectiveness of flipped classroom to mathematics achievement, their findings indicated that the strategy had a significant improvement to students achievement. The findings were further supported by the findings of Finkenberg & Trefzger (2019) from a quasi-experimental study conducted in German secondary schools and found that the flipped classroom method significantly improved students' performance in physics. The experimental group showed higher test scores compared to students taught through traditional methods. The improved performance in physics was attributed to better conceptual understanding and more active learning opportunities in the flipped classroom model.

5. CONCLUSION

The objective of the study was to determine the effect of the flipped classroom strategy on academic achievement of physics. In this study four groups were randomly selected where two of them were experimental groups while the other two control groups. One experimental group and one control group did a pretest achievement test, their performance were recorded. An independent t-test was conducted with the help of SPSS 16 with $\alpha = 0.05$ between the scores of E1 pretest and the C1 pretest scores to test whether the groups were of the same capacity before the treatment. The significances of the 2-tailed t tests were 0.802 and 0.805 for equal variance assumed and equal variance not assumed respectively. 0.802 And $0.805 > 0.05$, therefore, there was no statistical difference between the pretest achievement scores of E1 and those of C1. Following this, a conclusion was made that the two groups were initially of the same level before the treatment. A one-way ANOVA test was done to compare the variance between all the experimental groups and the control groups' posttest achievement scores to determine their statistical difference with a confidence level of 0.05 with the help of SPSS 16. The critical value obtained from the analysis of variance was 0.036. Since $0.036 < 0.05$ hence the null hypothesis stated earlier was rejected. Therefore, this value indicates that flipped classroom strategy significantly improve students' academic achievement in physics.

6. RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study the following recommendations are made:

- i. Teachers should be employing flipped classroom strategy as an instructional method when teaching learners who achieve dismally in physics in order to improve their physics performance.
- ii. The ministry of education, through the teachers service commission and teacher training institutions, should integrate flipped classroom training in teacher professional development programmers for effective adoption of learner-centered approaches, particularly in physics and other stem subjects.
- iii. The government and educational stakeholders should invest in improving ICT infrastructure in rural schools to ensure sustainability and equitable access to digital learning resources.

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International Journal of Novel Research in Education and Learning

 Vol. 12, Issue 3, pp: (23-33), Month: May - June 2025, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

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